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ANALYSIS OF LEADING SECTORS ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE PROVINCE OF WEST NUSA TENGGARA IN 2010-2023

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Abstract

This research aims to analyze the leading sectors in the Province of West Nusa Tenggara using quantitative methods and secondary data, specifically the Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) of West Nusa Tenggara Province as the observation area and Indonesia's GRDP as the reference area, covering the period from 2010 to 2023. The study employs Location Quotient (LQ) and Shift Share analyses to identify key sectors contributing to regional economic growth. The LQ analysis identifies seven leading sectors in the province, namely Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries; Mining and Quarrying; Transportation and Warehousing; Public Administration, Defense, and Compulsory Social Security; Education Services; Health Services and Social Activities; and Other Services. Meanwhile, the Shift Share analysis reveals that nine sectors exhibit positive growth, and five sectors hold comparative advantages. Combining these analytical approaches, sectors with $LQ > 1$ and Positive Base (PB) > 0 are categorized as leading sectors, which include the Education Services, Health Services and Social Activities, and Other Services sectors. These findings provide insights into the region's economic strengths and can guide policymakers in formulating strategies for sustainable development.

Key Words: Leading Sector, Location Quotient, Shift Share

INTRODUCTION

High and sustainable economic growth is a condition and necessity for the sustainability of economic development to improve people's welfare. Due to the increasing population every year resulting in increased consumption needs every year, an increase in income is needed every year (Tambunan, 2003: 40).

Economic growth is the development of activities in the economy that result in an increase in the value of goods and services produced in a region that will increase the prosperity of society. The problem of economic growth can be seen as a macroeconomic problem over a long period of time. From one period to another the ability to produce goods and services will increase, this is because the factors of production will always increase in quantity and the quality of goods and services will increase (Sukirno, 1998: 10).

Economic growth is a benchmark for the economy of a region, rapid and sustainable economic growth is the main condition or a necessity for the sustainability of economic development and improved welfare. Economic growth is a condition in which the

state of the economy of a region continuously experiences an increase in a much better situation than before in a certain period of time. In an effort to encourage the economy to be better, it is very necessary for the role of the government to explore the potential possessed in a region, and must also be supported by qualified human resources and experts in their respective fields in order to manage natural resources properly and efficiently so that they can meet the economic needs of the region and the benefits can be felt by many people.(Ristawan et al., 2022).

Economic growth in a region is influenced by three main components, namely national economic growth or regional share (PR) in the first component is used to analyze sectoral changes in GRDP in a province by comparing the same sector sectors from a larger region, the second is proportional shift used to measure changes in relative growth in the province compared to the national economy, and the third is a shift in competitiveness or differential shift (PD) which determines how far the competitiveness of a sector in the region (Tambunan, 2003).

GRDP Per Capita of Indonesian Provinces at Constant Prices 2010-2023 (In Billion Rupiah)

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics

Based on graph showing Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) per capita by province in Indonesia from 2012-2023, it can be seen that NTB Province has a relatively low GRDP when compared to other provinces such as DKI Jakarta, East Java and East Kalimantan, this shows that the average income in NTB is still lower than other provinces. However, if West Nusa Tenggara is compared to eastern Indonesia such as East Nusa Tenggara (NTT), and Papua, NTB's GDRP per capita is higher because NTB's economic potential is stronger than some provinces in eastern Indonesia.

Economic growth is a macro indicator used to see the real performance of an economy in a region. The rate of economic growth can be seen from the change in GRDP at constant prices in the year concerned with the previous year. Economic growth can also be seen as an increase in the amount of goods and services produced by several economic sectors in a region within 1 year (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2024).

The leading sector is an economic activity in an area that has expertise in serving the demand of a consumer or community both in the domestic market and outside the region itself, the area indirectly has the expertise to maximize the potential results of the area, manage and market all commodities that can be made in the area in totality (Soleh & Maryoni, 2017).

A region certainly has different natural characteristics in each region both in terms of geographical location, human resources, different facilities and infrastructure and soil fertility because of this, a region must determine what sector is the leading sector. Each region must have the advantage of natural resources and human resources that are different from other regions, this can be seen from the growth and role of the existing sectors. Regional analysis is needed in order to know which sector is the leading sector or base sector, to know which sector is developing and which sector is lagging behind, so that it can be done to determine the priority sector in the management of a region.

Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) is the gross value added of all goods and services produced by a domestic area or produced in a country that arises as a result of various economic activities in a certain period without regard to the production factor resident or non-resident. GRDP is prepared through three approaches, namely the production approach, the expenditure approach and income based on constant prices and at current prices (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2024).

West Nusa Tenggara Province (NTB) is a province in the eastern part of Indonesia which is divided into 2 islands, namely Lombok island and Sumbawa island and consists of 10 districts and cities, each of which has a different leading sector in each district and city, human resources and natural resources that are also different in each region.

According to constant 2010 prices, the value of GRDP increased from 102.07 trillion rupiah in 2022 to 103.91 trillion rupiah in 2023. This situation shows that the state of the NTB economy during 2023 experienced a growth of 1.80 percent. The increase in the value of GRDP is due to increased production in several sectors of the business field category and the increase in the sector is not influenced by inflation. The role of various business sectors in the production of goods and services determines the economic structure in a region. The value of the contribution generated by the sector can determine how important the sector is in improving the economy of a region (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2024)

GRDP at Constant Prices of NTB Province by Business Field in 2010-2023 (Billion Rupiah)

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics

Based on data from the Central Bureau of Statistics of West Nusa Tenggara Province in 2012-2023 in graph above, the sector that has the largest contribution to GRDP in NTB is dominated by 7 categories of business field sectors, namely: Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries; Mining and Quarrying; Wholesale and Retail Trade, Car and Motorcycle Repair; Transportation and Warehousing; Government Administration, Defense and Social Security; Education Services; and Construction Sector.

The state of the West Nusa Tenggara economy in 2013 experienced an increase when compared to 2012 according to GRDP at constant prices. GRDP value in 2013 reached 17,702 billion rupiah, an increase when compared to 2012 which reached 16,946 billion rupiah.

In 2015 and 2016, the sector that made a significant contribution to NTB's GRDP was the mining and quarrying sector. In 2015, the contribution of the mining and quarrying sector amounted to 23.175 billion rupiah and in 2016 amounted to 24.501 billion rupiah. However, in 2017-2020 this sector experienced a decrease in GRDP revenue.

The decline in GRDP in the Mining and Quarrying sector in 2017-2020 was due to the factor of reducing the amount of production by PT Amman Mineral Nusa Tenggara, the company is the largest mining company in NTB, so that in 2017 to 2020 the contribution of the mining and quarrying sector was replaced by the agriculture, forestry and fisheries sector and the wholesale and retail trade sector which had a GRDP value of 13.856 billion rupiah in 2017 and the agriculture, forestry and fisheries sector of 20.834 billion rupiah.

In 2020-2022 the sector that has contributed to the NTB economy is the government administration sector, defense and mandatory social security. Conversely, in 2019 the sector that has the greatest role in the formation of West Nusa Tenggara GRDP is the transportation and storage sector. In 2023 the Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries sector reached 22.23 percent, the figure this year is lower than in 2019, followed by the Mining and Quarrying sector at 17.93 percent. The contribution of this sector can be seen from its influence on the formation of West Nusa Tenggara GRDP.

The relevant research that is the source of this research is research conducted by Rimasyah Noor (2023) entitled "Leading Sector Analysis in Regencies and cities of NTB Province in 2015-2021". This research has an equation to analyze the leading and non leading sectors using the calculation of LQ and Shift Share analysis. Then this research also has similarities with research conducted by Yuni Purnama Dkk (2017) entitled "Analysis of Leading Sectors and Structural Shifts in Increasing NTB Economic Growth 2000-2015". This research has similarities, namely analyzing the leading sector in NTB Province using the calculation method of LQ and Shift Share analysis.

Based on the description above, the way to identify the business sector that will become the leading sector in a region requires several efforts such as further developing and prioritizing regional development in accordance with the economic potential and leading sectors in the Regency / City in West Nusa Tenggara province. To find out the leading sector in the district / city in West Nusa Tenggara Province, a method is needed to analyze in order to facilitate policy making. Therefore, researchers are interested in analyzing the "Analysis of the influence of the Leading Sector on Economic Growth in West Nusa Tenggara Province in 2010-2023".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Economic Development

According to Sukirno (2001) in (Efendi et al., 2022) Economic development is a process that causes the per capita income of the population in a country to increase in the long term. This definition implies that economic development is a change that will occur continuously until it reaches something better such as an increase in the real income per capita of the population over a long period of time.

Economic Growth

Economic growth is a process of increasing per capita output that occurs continuously over a long period of time. Economic growth is one indicator of the success of economic development, the higher the economic growth will lead to increased public welfare (Sukirno, 2000).

Regional Economic Development

Regional economic development is a process in which local governments and communities manage existing resources and form a pattern of local government partnerships with the private sector to create new jobs and stimulate the development of economic activity in the region (Arsyad, 2004).

Economic Base Theory

Base theory is the main determinant of economic growth in a region that is directly related to the demand for goods and services from outside the region. The production process in sectors in a region that use local production resources (SDP), inputs and outputs are exported will generate economic growth, an increase in per capita income will create employment opportunities in the region (Tambunan, 2003).

Leading Sector

Leading sectors are usually related to regional, national and international scale comparisons. On an international scale a sector can be said to be superior when the sector is able to compete with the same sector in other countries. While in the national context, a sector is said to be a leading sector if the region can win the competition in the same sector with other regions both national and domestic markets to produce exports (T. Tambunan, 2001).

Gross Regional Domestic Product

According to (Kuncoro, 2015) the definition of Gross Regional Domestic Product is divided into two definitions, namely domestic products and domestic and regional areas. Domestic products are goods and services produced from economic activity in the domestic region regardless of whether the production factors come from residents in the region. Some of the production factors owned by a region come from other regions or countries, otherwise the production factors produced in the region are used by other regions. Domestic and regional areas are provinces or regions in a country.

RESEARCH METHODS

Types of Research and Data Sources

The type of data used in this study is secondary data in the form of panel data, which is a combination of time series and cross section data. Secondary data is a data source that is obtained indirectly to data collectors. Secondary data is obtained from sources that can support research such as documentation or literature (Sugiyono, 2013).

The data source intended here is data obtained from the official website of the Central Bureau of Statistics such as GRDP data by Business Field in NTB Province (Billion Rupiah) 2010-2023 and GRDP data by Business Field in Indonesia (Billion Rupiah) 2010-2023.

To answer the problem formulation and research objectives using analysis, namely Location Quotien and shift share analysis. An explanation of the analytical tools used as follows:

Location Quotien (LQ) Analysis

Location Quotien (LQ) analysis is an analytical tool to see the economic base of a region. This analysis is usually used to see which sector is the highest and lowest producer and which sector has the most influence on the economy. Some conditions for the sector to be categorized as a basic sector are as follows

- a. If the coefficient value of the Location Quotien (LQ) analysis > 1 then the sector can be categorized as a basic or leading sector and is very influential on the regional economy.
- b. If the coefficient value of LQ < 1 then the sector cannot be categorized as a leading sector and cannot be exported outside the region.
- c. If the LQ coefficient value = 1 then the sector is not a mainstay sector where the sector has not developed enough and needs further management.

According to (Tambunan, 2003) to analyze the leading sector using Location Quotien (LQ) analysis with the formula:

$$LQ = \frac{v_i/v_t}{V_i/V_t}$$

Description:

v_i = GRDP of Sector i in the Province

v_t = Total GRDP of the Province

V_i = National GDP of sector i

V_t = National total GRDP

Shift Share Analysis

Shift Share analysis is an analytical tool to determine the economic performance and labor productivity of a region by comparing it with the economy in a wider region or compared with the national economy.

According to (Sjafrizal, 2018) the Shift Share calculation can be derived from the formula for each component of the Shift Share model as follows:

1. National Growth Component (Regional Share)

The National Growth Component (Regional Share) is a component of economic growth caused by external factors such as increased regional economic activity due to national policies that apply to all regions. This component can be seen from the following equation:

$$KPN = \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i(Y^t/Y^0 - 1)]$$

Description:

y = Value added in sector i in the Province at the beginning of the period

Y_0 = Value added in sector i in the National at the beginning of the period

Y_t = Value added in sector i in the National at the end of the period.

2. Proportional Growth Component (Proportionality Shift)

The Proportional Growth Component reflects the change in the level of regional economic output resulting from a change in the proportion of regional output to national/provincial output.

$$KPP = \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i(Y_i^t/Y_i^0) - (Y_i^t/Y_i^0)]$$

Description:

y = Value added in sector i in the Province at the beginning of the period

Y_{0i} = Value added in sector i in the National at the beginning of the period

Y_{ti} = Value added in sector i in the National at the end of the period.

3. Regional Growth Share Component (Differential Shift)

The Regional Share Growth Component (Differential Shift) is a component of regional economic growth due to differential shifts that will determine how far the competitiveness of a sector in the district/city compared to the same sector in the province/nation.

$$KPPW = \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i(y_i^t/y_i^0) - (Y_i^t/Y_i^0)]$$

Description:

y_i = Value added in sector i

y_{0i} = Value added in sector i in the province at the beginning of the period

y_{ti} = Value added in sector i in the province at the end of the period.

ANALYSIS RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Location Quotien Analysis Results

Results of Location Quotien Analysis of NTB Province in 2010-2023

Business Field	LQ						
	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries	1.53	1.55	1.55	1.53	1.53	1.58	1.58
Mining and Quarrying	2.79	1.92	1.37	1.39	1.38	2.96	3.10
Processing Industry	0.21	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.19	0.19	0.19
Electricity and Gas Procurement	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.07	0.07
Water Supply, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling	0.87	0.88	0.88	0.89	0.90	0.88	0.89
Construction	0.89	0.88	0.86	0.85	0.85	0.86	0.89
Wholesale and Retail Trade; Repair of Cars and Motorcycles	0.76	0.74	0.77	0.79	0.81	0.84	0.87
Transportation and Warehousing	1.65	1.63	1.62	1.60	1.60	1.59	1.55
Provision of Accommodation and Drinking Food	0.48	0.49	0.49	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.53
Information and Communication	0.46	0.46	0.45	0.44	0.43	0.42	0.42
Financial Services and Insurance	0.61	0.65	0.67	0.67	0.69	0.70	0.72
Real Estate	0.84	0.83	0.83	0.84	0.84	0.86	0.88
Company Services	0.10	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.09	0.09	0.09
Government Administration, Defense and Compulsory Social Security	1.44	1.37	1.35	1.36	1.39	1.38	1.37
Education Services	1.28	1.30	1.25	1.23	1.24	1.24	1.27
Health and Social Services	1.77	1.71	1.64	1.63	1.62	1.62	1.64
Other Services	1.24	1.24	1.20	1.22	1.21	1.19	1.17

Bussines Fiels	LQ								Description
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Average	
Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries	1.62	1.59	1.56	1.52	1.51	1.51	1.52	1.55	ADVANTAGES
Mining and Quarrying	2.47	1.60	1.58	2.06	1.97	2.32	1.96	2.06	ADVANTAGES
Processing Industry	0.20	0.19	0.19	0.19	0.19	0.19	0.18	0.19	NON ADVANTAGES
Electricity and Gas Procurement	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.07	NON ADVANTAGES
Water Supply, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling	0.89	0.82	0.79	0.79	0.75	0.75	0.73	0.84	NON ADVANTAGES
Construction	0.89	0.87	0.92	0.81	0.86	0.83	0.88	0.87	NON ADVANTAGED
Wholesale and Retail Trade; Repair of Cars and Motorcycles	0.90	0.91	0.92	0.91	0.89	0.88	0.90	0.85	NON ADVANTAGED
Transportation and Warehousing	1.53	1.46	1.39	1.13	1.11	1.09	1.03	1.43	ADVANTAGES
Provision of Accommodation and Drinking Food	0.54	0.49	0.46	0.37	0.36	0.40	0.40	0.47	NON ADVANTAGED
Information and Communication	0.42	0.41	0.39	0.40	0.39	0.38	0.37	0.42	NON ADVANTAGED
Financial Services and Insurance	0.75	0.77	0.73	0.79	0.81	0.80	0.75	0.72	NON ADVANTAGED
Real Estate	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.89	0.88	0.90	0.93	0.87	NON ADVANTAGED
Company Services	0.09	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.09	NON ADVANTAGED
Government Administration, Defense and Compulsory Social Security	1.39	1.31	1.30	1.34	1.37	1.36	1.35	1.36	ADVANTAGES
Education Services	1.30	1.30	1.31	1.29	1.31	1.34	1.39	1.29	ADVANTAGES
Health and Social Services	1.63	1.64	1.61	1.41	1.37	1.37	1.39	1.57	ADVANTAGES
Other Services	1.15	1.11	1.06	1.03	1.03	1.04	1.00	1.13	ADVANTAGES

In the analysis, it was found that in 2010-2023 there were 7 leading sectors in West Nusa Tenggara Province, namely: 1) Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries Sector, 2) Mining and Quarrying Sector, 3) Transportation and Warehousing Sector, 4) Government Administration, Defense and Compulsory Social Security Sector, 5) Education Services Sector, 6) Health Services and Social Activities Sector, 7) Other Services Sector.

Economic Growth in the agriculture, forestry and fisheries sector category fluctuates annually, during the last 14 years (2010-2023) shows an LQ value of 1.55 which means the LQ value > 1 means that the agriculture, forestry and fisheries sector has a large contribution to the formation of NTB GRDP compared to other sectors. The high contribution of the agricultural sector shows that the structure of the NTB economy is an agrarian structure which is dominated by the agriculture, forestry and fisheries sector as well as the mining and quarrying sector.

The contribution of the mining and quarrying sector to the formation of NTB's GRDP for 15 years can be categorized as large due to the LQ coefficient value of 2.06 which means the coefficient (>1). The magnitude of the LQ value in this sector is in accordance with Law No.33 of 2004 article 14 (3) which states that the proceeds from general mining revenues generated from the region concerned, divided by a balance of 20 percent for the government and 80 percent for the region.

The contribution of the Transportation and Warehousing sector to the formation of NTB GRDP for 15 years can be categorized as large due to the LQ coefficient value of 1.43 which means the coefficient (>1). The high value of LQ in this sector is caused by transportation activities in NTB Province which experienced various significant changes due to the increasing number of passengers coming both by sea, as well as through domestic flights and international flights.

Based on BPS data on the sea transportation sector, the number of arrivals and departures through the sea port amounted to 99.85 and 96.79 thousand people, the number of passengers arriving rose 8.63 percent and departing rose 4.26 percent. For the aviation sector, the number of domestic flight passengers rose 3.18 percent to reach 95,749 people and international flights jumped significantly by 59.76 percent to 16,200 people.

The contribution of the government administration, defense and mandatory social security sector to the formation of NTB's GRDP for 14 years can be categorized as large due to the LQ coefficient value of 1.36 which means the coefficient (>1). The category of government administration, defense and compulsory social security includes government activities carried out by government administration including legislation and legal interpreters related to the court and according to its regulations.

During the 14 year period from 2010-2023, the average LQ value of the Education services sector in NTB is 1.29 which means the LQ coefficient > 1 and this sector is categorized as a leading sector because it has a large contribution to the formation of West Nusa Tenggara GRDP.

The contribution of the Health Services sector and social activities to the formation of NTB's GRDP for 14 years can be categorized as large due to the LQ coefficient value of 1.57 which means the coefficient (>1). And this sector is a leading sector because it has a large contribution to the formation of NTB's GRDP.

While there are 10 non leading sectors in West Nusa Tenggara Province as follows: 1) Manufacturing Industry Sector, 2) Electricity and Gas Procurement Sector, 3) Water Supply, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling, 4) Construction, 5) Wholesale and Retail Trade; Car and Motorcycle Repair, 6) Food and Drink Accommodation Providers, 7) Information and Communication, 8) Financial and Insurance Services, 9) Real Estate, 10) Corporate Services.

Shift Share Analysis Results

Shift share analysis is an analytical tool to determine the economic performance and labor productivity of a region by comparing it with the economy in a wider region or compared to the national economy.

The National Growth Component (National Share) is the component of economic growth caused by external factors such as increased regional economic activity due to national policies that apply to all regions. The NVC is a change in production or employment opportunities in a region caused by changes in national economic policy and other policies that can affect the economic sector in a region. A positive NVC value indicates that the sector is experiencing growth in terms of economic value and if the NVC shows a negative number, it means that the sector is contracting.

Shift share calculation (KPN) of NTB Province 2010-2023

No	Business Field	NTB PROVINCE		NATIONAL		KPN	KPP	KPPW	PE
		2010	2023	2010	2023				
1	Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries	14.939.02	22.642.72	956.119.70	1.454.586.90	79.21	-27.08	-0.57	51.57
2	Mining and Quarrying	20.471.12	18.218.41	718.128.60	910.679.40	79.21	-52.40	-37.82	-11.00
3	Processing Industry	3.210.93	4.644.52	1.512.760.80	2.507.799.80	79.21	-13.44	-21.13	44.65
4	Electricity and Gas Procurement	34.90	118.67	72.549.10	128.460.50	79.21	-2.15	162.96	240.03
5	Water Supply, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling	51.75	80.41	5.848.50	10.741.40	79.21	4.45	-28.28	55.38
6	Construction	5.715.15	10.575.41	626.905.40	1.179.989.30	79.21	9.01	-3.18	85.04
7	Wholesale and Retail Trade; Repair of Cars and Motorcycles	7.136.90	14.737.70	923.923.80	1.604.114.00	79.21	-5.59	32.88	106.50
8	Transportation and Warehousing	4.140.34	5.844.05	245.375.40	554.854.90	79.21	46.91	-84.98	41.15
9	Provision of Accommodation and Drinking Food	988.89	1.556.05	200.281.80	382.674.50	79.21	11.86	-33.71	57.35
10	Information and Communication	1.211.82	3.014.95	256.048.10	807.304.60	79.21	136.08	-66.50	148.80
11	Financial Services and Insurance	1.490.07	3.818.83	239.728.40	496.236.80	79.21	27.79	49.29	156.29
12	Real Estate	1.695.62	3.267.52	198.213.50	343.864.80	79.21	-5.73	19.22	92.70
13	Company Services	97.95	195.86	99.085.40	232.076.10	79.21	55.01	-34.26	99.96
14	Government Administration, Defense and Compulsory Social Security	3.812.96	5.233.33	259.646.10	378.989.10	79.21	-33.25	-8.71	37.25
15	Education Services	2.643.37	5.080.27	201.559.50	358.952.10	79.21	-1.13	14.10	92.19
16	Health and Social Services	1.198.74	2.392.52	66.444.70	168.926.20	79.21	75.02	-54.65	99.59
17	Other Services	1.283.21	2.484.71	101.061.00	242.891.70	79.21	61.13	-46.71	93.63

Based on the results of the Shift Share analysis above, the value of the national growth component (Regional Share) in West Nusa Tenggara Province shows a positive value with a Regional Share value of 79.21, which means that the province's growth is caused by external factors. In NTB Province the only sector that has rapid growth and has a comparative advantage is the Health and Insurance Services Sector.

The Proportional Growth Component reflects changes in regional economic output levels resulting from changes in the proportion of regional output to national/provincial output. PPP is an important indicator in determining the sustainability of economic growth. A positive PPP value in a region indicates that the sector is growing fast nationally or that the efficiency of resource use in the sector is increasing. Conversely, if the value of KPP is negative, it indicates that the sector is growing slowly nationally or the productivity of the sector is decreasing.

Based on the results of Shift Share analysis, there are 8 sectors that have slow growth and 9 sectors that have fast growth. Sectors that have positive KPP values are sector 1) Water supply, waste management, waste and recycling, 2) Construction, 3) Transportation and Warehousing, 4) Provision of food and beverage accommodation, 5) Information and Communication, 6) Financial and Insurance Services, 7) Corporate Services, 8) Health Services and Social Activities, 9) Other Services. These sectors have a positive value because they contribute well to the national economy. Sectors that have negative LTO values are sectors 1) Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries, 2) Mining and Quarrying, 3) Manufacturing Industry, 4) Electricity and Gas Procurement, 5) Wholesale and Retail Trade; Car and Motorcycle Repair, 6) Real Estate, 7) Government Administration, Defense and Compulsory Social Security, 8) Educational Services. These sectors have a negative KPP value because they have slow growth. The fastest growing sector is the information and communication sector at 136.0815 and the slowest growing sector is the mining and quarrying sector at -52.3998.

The Regional Growth Share Component (Differential Shift) is a component of regional economic growth due to differential shifts that will determine how far the competitiveness of a sector in the district/city compared to the same sector in the province/nation. KPPW is positive for sectors that have comparative advantage or have high competitiveness in the region. Conversely, if the KPPW value is negative, it means that the sector does not have a comparative advantage or has low competitiveness.

Based on the analysis results in the table above, it shows that there are 5 sectors that have comparative advantage and 12 sectors that do not have comparative advantage. Sectors that have comparative advantage include; 1) Electricity and gas procurement, 2) Wholesale and Retail Trade, Car and Motorcycle Repair, 3) Financial and Insurance Services, 4) Real Estate, 5) Education Services. These sectors have a positive value because when compared to other sectors in the same region the sector contributes well to NTB Province. Sectors that do not have comparative advantage are as follows: 1) Agriculture, forestry and fisheries, 2) Mining and Quarrying, 3) Processing Industry, 4) Water Supply, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling, 5) Construction, 6) Transportation and Warehousing, 7) provision of Accommodation and Drinking Food, 8) Information and Communication, 9) Corporate Services, 10) Government Administration, Defense and Compulsory Social Security, 11) Health Services and Social Activities, 12) Other Services. The sector that has a high

comparative advantage is the Electricity and gas procurement sector at 162.9617 and the sector that has the lowest comparative advantage is the transportation and warehousing sector at -84.9759.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion that the author has described above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Based on Location Quotien analysis, the results obtained, in the period 2010 - 2023 there are 7 leading sectors in West Nusa Tenggara Province, namely: 1) Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries Sector, 2) Mining and Quarrying Sector, 3) Transportation and Warehousing Sector, 4) Government Administration, Defense and Compulsory Social Security Sector, 5) Education Services Sector, 6) Health Services and Social Activities Sector, 7) Other Services Sector.
2. Based on the results of the Shift Share analysis, the following results were obtained:
 - a. National Growth Component,
The value of the national growth component (Regional Share) in West Nusa Tenggara Province shows a positive value with a Regional Share value of 79.21, which means that the province's growth is caused by external factors.
 - b. Proportional Growth Component
Sectors that have a positive PPP value and are running fast are sectors 1) Water supply, waste management, waste and recycling, 2) Construction, 3) Transportation and Warehousing, 4) Provision of food and beverage accommodation, 5) Information and Communication, 6) Financial and Insurance Services, 7) Corporate Services, 8) Health and Social Services, 9) Other Services. These sectors receive a positive value because they contribute well to the national economy.
 - c. Growth Component of Regional Share
There are 5 sectors that have comparative advantage and 12 sectors that do not have comparative advantage. Sectors that have comparative advantage include; 1) Electricity and gas procurement, 2) Wholesale and Retail Trade, Car and Motorcycle Repair, 3) Financial and Insurance Services, 4) Real Estate, 5) Education Services. These sectors have a positive value because when compared to other sectors in the same region the sector contributes well to NTB Province.

Suggestion

In encouraging the economy of West Nusa Tenggara, the government needs to prioritize the development of leading sectors that have a significant impact on regional economic growth. The budget for this leading sector needs to be increased so that its growth is more optimal and able to encourage other sectors to develop. In addition, it is recommended that the government not only focus on developing the sectors that make the largest contribution to NTB's GRDP, but also pay attention to non-superior sectors because the linkages between sectors support regional economic development.

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